

VOYAGE ONE – Audience Mobile Phone Orchestra Performance

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

Voyage One is a 6-minute composition for a participatory Mobile Phone Orchestra (MPO) concept developed by Anders Lind. The MPO concept is designed to embrace people regardless their musical backgrounds as performers, but still with an aim to generate expressive and meaningful artistic expressions for concert hall performances. In a performance the MPO consist of 20-40 people, divided in 6 individual parts. They perform using their phones, and the dedicated MPO Web-API, as instrument interfaces. Animated notation is showing performance instructions for the 6 individual parts and conducting the performance. Voyage One was composed in 2017, during the early stages of development of the MPO platform. The work is a single movement composition, where 6 individual voices are introduced one after another to slowly build up an orchestral harmonic texture towards a concluding climax. The composition is characterized by tight constraints, where only four pitches are used in each voice, based on the previous conditions of the mobile phone orchestra's instrument interface. The challenge lay in creating musical coherence within this limitation of four pitches per voice by organizing the interaction among the six voices. For NIME 2024 Voyage One is performed by the audience at the conference.

Fig. 1. Photo from Mobile Phone Orchestra performance

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2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

In his ongoing artistic research and artistic work, Lind is exploring strategies for creating inclusive participatory, but still expressive, performances within contemporary art music. Voyage One was composed as part of his ongoing artistic research at Umeå University in Sweden, which aims to explore artistic possibilities in high-agency participatory mobile phone orchestra settings. Mobilephoneorchestra.com is a Web-API concept developed by Anders Lind in collaboration with Björn Yttergren (programmer) and Håkan Gustafsson (graphic designer). The concept has similarities with a traditional philharmonic orchestra, but utilizes electronic sounds and embraces people regardless musical backgrounds as performers. The MPO concept is developed for performances of polyphonic electronic music both for standalone MPO and for MPO together with traditional orchestra, ensemble, soloist settings [fig.3]. Three main criteria were established to fulfil the ambitions of this MPO concept: easy access, mobile and artistically rewarding. Easy access refers both to the availability of the platform as well as being user-friendly to people, regardless of their musical background. The mobile criteria refers to mobility and its availability for use in a wide range of areas and spaces. Artistically rewarding refers to the aim of both providing meaningful and active participation experiences, through a high agency concept, and still generate expressive and flexible artistic expressions suited for concert hall performances. The main challenge has been the development of a MPO concept that could both facilitate flexible and expressive artistic output, and still be easy-access and mobile, embracing people regardless their musical backgrounds as performers. We have argued that the key for fulfilling the aims of this MPO concept has been the use of animated notation [fig.2], with a computer game inspired approach, which could provide accessible multiple part performance instructions during performance [1]. Several compositions for the MPO concept has been performed in various conference settings and concert hall settings since the first development stages in 2017 [2][3][4]. Currently Lind is collaborating, in a three year artistic research project, with an opera house in Sweden to explore and implement strategies for involving the MPO concept in concert hall performances of contemporary art music.

Fig. 2. Example of the Animated notation for the MPO performance

Fig. 3. Illustration of a performance setting involving the Mobile Phone Orchestra and String Quartet.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

For the performance of Voyage One (stand-alone Mobile Phone Orchestra) **the audience at the conference becomes the Mobile Phone Orchestra. A projector is needed from the NIME organization** to provide for showing the animated notation (video file provided by composer) during performance. **5-10 minutes of performance instructions for the audience will introduce** the performance (led by the composer). The performance of Voyage One at NIME 2024 may take place in various spaces. Performance at NIME 2024 may take place at the Tivoli Vredenburg as well in the local Utrecht stages as long as there are possibilities to show the animated notation on a projector.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Video link to excerpts of some previous performances including the Mobile Phone Orchestra: <https://share.mediaflow.com/se/?17LELY7PS0>
- Audio of Voyage One - live performance: <https://youtu.be/8zEm0X3xPOM>

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